

Medical Ethic Cases

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Analyzed Chronological Studies and Summary

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Medical ethics is a branch of ethics that deals with moral principles and values related to medical practice and healthcare. It provides a framework for guiding healthcare professionals, researchers, and institutions in making morally sound decisions in the field of medicine. Medical ethics is essential for ensuring patient welfare, promoting just and equitable healthcare practices, and maintaining the trust between healthcare providers and patients.

Key principles and concepts within medical ethics include:

1. **Autonomy:** Respecting the patient's right to make their own decisions about their medical treatment, including the right to refuse treatment.
2. **Beneficence:** Acting in the best interests of the patient and promoting their well-being.
3. **Nonmaleficence:** Avoiding harm to the patient and minimizing potential harm when providing medical care.
4. **Justice:** Ensuring fairness and equality in the distribution of healthcare resources and treatment options.
5. **Veracity:** Being truthful and honest with patients while providing information about their medical condition and treatment options.
6. **Confidentiality:** Safeguarding patient information and maintaining their privacy.
7. **Fidelity:** Maintaining trust and loyalty in the patient-physician relationship.
8. **Respect for Persons:** Treating patients with respect, regardless of their background, beliefs, or circumstances.
9. **Informed Consent:** Obtaining the voluntary and informed agreement of a patient before proceeding with medical treatment or procedures.
10. **End-of-Life Care:** Addressing ethical issues related to patients at the end of their lives, such as withholding or withdrawing life-sustaining treatments, palliative care, and assisted dying.
11. **Research Ethics:** Ensuring that research involving human subjects follows ethical guidelines, including informed consent, minimizing risks, and maximizing benefits.
12. **Resource Allocation:** Making ethical decisions about how to distribute limited healthcare resources, especially in cases of scarcity or emergency situations.

Medical ethics often involves challenging dilemmas where principles may conflict, such as respecting a patient's autonomy while also considering their best interests. Ethical considerations may vary across cultures, legal frameworks, and medical traditions, but the core principles aim to provide a moral compass for medical professionals to navigate complex situations.

Ethical dilemmas in medicine can involve topics like end-of-life care, reproductive rights, organ transplantation, genetic testing, experimental treatments, and the use of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence in healthcare.

Healthcare professionals, researchers, policymakers, and institutions typically follow ethical guidelines and codes of conduct set by medical associations and regulatory bodies to ensure that their practices align with the principles of medical ethics and contribute to the well-being of patients and society as a whole.

Milgram experiment 1961 United States

The Milgram experiment on obedience to authority figures was a series of notable social psychology experiments conducted by Yale University psychologist Stanley Milgram, which measured the willingness of study participants to obey an authority figure who instructed them to perform acts that conflicted with their personal conscience.[17] The detailed findings are discussed in his 1974 book, *Obedience to Authority: An Experimental View*. [18] The experiments were controversial, and considered by some scientists to be unethical and physically or psychologically abusive. Psychologist Diana Baumrind considered the experiment "harmful because it may cause permanent psychological damage and cause people to be less trusting in the future.

Summary: The Milgram Experiment, conducted in 1961 by psychologist Stanley Milgram, was a highly influential study that aimed to investigate the extent to which individuals would obey authority figures, even when their actions went against their own conscience or moral values. The experiment was designed to explore the factors that might lead people to engage in acts that they would typically consider ethically or morally wrong.

Here's an overview of the Milgram Experiment:

Experiment Design: Participants were recruited for what they were told was a study on the effects of punishment on learning. They were informed that they would play the role of a "teacher" and would administer electric shocks to a "learner" (who was actually an actor pretending to receive shocks) every time the learner answered a question incorrectly. The "learner" was placed in a separate room, and the "teacher" was seated in front of an electric shock generator with switches labeled with voltage levels, ranging from 15 to 450 volts. The shocks were not real, but the "teacher" believed they were administering increasingly severe shocks with each incorrect answer.

Findings: The most notable finding of the Milgram Experiment was that a significant percentage of participants were willing to deliver the maximum voltage shock (450 volts) to the "learner," even though the learner's protests and apparent pain were clearly evident. The experiment found that factors like the presence of an authoritative figure, the gradual escalation of shocks, and the social pressure to continue played a significant role in influencing participants to obey.

Ethical Concerns: The Milgram Experiment raised significant ethical concerns due to the psychological distress experienced by participants. Many participants showed signs of stress, anxiety, and guilt during the experiment. They were misled about the true nature of the experiment, and some experienced emotional trauma as a result. However, Milgram argued that the insights gained into human obedience justified the temporary discomfort experienced by participants.

Implications: The Milgram Experiment highlighted the powerful influence of authority figures and social pressures on individual behavior. It raised questions about the capacity of ordinary

people to commit morally objectionable acts when placed in certain contexts. The study's findings have been used to understand phenomena like conformity, obedience, and the potential for unethical behavior within organizational settings, including situations like the Holocaust. While the Milgram Experiment provided valuable insights into human behavior, it also sparked debates about the ethical treatment of participants and the need to prioritize their well-being in psychological research. In modern research, ethical guidelines and review processes have become more stringent to ensure the protection of participants' rights and well-being.

The Declaration of Helsinki is a set of ethical principles and guidelines for conducting medical research involving human participants. It was adopted by the World Medical Association (WMA) and has served as a cornerstone document for ensuring the ethical conduct of medical research on a global scale. The declaration was first adopted in 1964 and has been revised multiple times to address emerging ethical concerns and changes in medical research practices. Key principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki include:

1. **Respect for Autonomy:** Participants have the right to make informed decisions about their participation in research, and their consent must be obtained after providing them with adequate information.
2. **Beneficence and Non-Maleficence:** Research should aim to benefit participants and society, while minimizing potential harm. Researchers must carefully weigh the risks and benefits of the research.
3. **Justice:** The selection of research participants should be fair and not exploit vulnerable or disadvantaged groups. The benefits and burdens of research should be distributed equitably.
4. **Informed Consent:** Participants should be fully informed about the research purpose, methods, risks, and benefits before providing their voluntary and informed consent.
5. **Privacy and Confidentiality:** Participant privacy must be protected, and their personal information should remain confidential.
6. **Ethical Review:** Research involving human participants should undergo independent ethical review by a research ethics committee to ensure that it aligns with ethical standards.
7. **Placebo Use:** The use of placebos in research should be justified when there are no proven interventions for a particular condition, and participants should not be denied effective treatment.
8. **Post-Trial Access:** Participants who have completed a research study should have access to any interventions or treatments proven effective during the study.
9. **Publication and Reporting:** Researchers have a responsibility to publish and report their research findings, regardless of whether the results are positive or negative.

The Declaration of Helsinki has had a significant impact on the ethical conduct of medical research, serving as a guide for researchers, institutions, and ethical review boards. It reflects the evolving understanding of ethical considerations in medical research and aims to protect the rights and well-being of research participants while promoting scientific advancement. While the Declaration of Helsinki provides a global framework for ethical research conduct, it's important to note that specific regulations and guidelines may vary by country or region.

Researchers and institutions are expected to adhere to both the general principles of the Declaration and any additional local regulations that apply to them.

Surgical removal of body parts to try to improve mental health 1920s

Controversial psychiatrist Henry Cotton at Trenton State Hospital in New Jersey became convinced that insanity was fundamentally a toxic disorder and he surgically removed body parts to try to improve mental health

The Monster Study 1939 United States

The Monster Study is the name given to a stuttering experiment performed on orphan children in Davenport, Iowa in 1939. It was conducted by Wendell Johnson at the University of Iowa. The research began with the selection of 22 subjects from a veterans' orphanage in Iowa. None were told the intent of the research, and they believed that they were to receive speech therapy. The study was trying to induce stuttering in healthy children. The experiment became national news in the San Jose Mercury News in 2001, and a book was written. On 17 August 2007, six of the orphan children were awarded \$925,000 by the State of Iowa for lifelong psychological and emotional scars caused by six months of torment during the Iowa University experiment. Although none of the children became stutterers, some became self-conscious and reluctant to speak.[5] A spokesman for the University of Iowa called the experiment "regrettable".

The Monster Study 1939

The Monster Study, also known as the "Iowa Speech-Sound Development Study," was an ethically controversial psychological experiment conducted in 1939 by Wendell Johnson and Mary Tudor at the University of Iowa. The study aimed to investigate the effects of negative speech therapy on children's speech development and self-esteem. However, the study's methods and impact on participants have led to criticism and ethical concerns.

Here's an overview of the Monster Study:

Experiment Design: The experiment involved orphaned children who were already experiencing speech problems. The researchers divided the children into two groups: one group received positive and supportive speech therapy, while the other group received negative and critical speech therapy.

In the "negative" therapy group, the children were subjected to consistent criticism, labeling their speech as "stuttering" even when they didn't actually have speech problems. This approach aimed to induce speech problems and observe the effects of negative reinforcement.

Findings: The experiment was meant to investigate whether negative speech therapy could worsen speech problems and affect self-esteem. The results suggested that children in the "negative" therapy group did experience increased speech difficulties and lower self-esteem compared to the "positive" therapy group.

Ethical Concerns and Criticisms: The Monster Study has faced severe ethical criticism over the years due to the emotional and psychological harm inflicted on vulnerable orphaned children. The children in the "negative" therapy group were subjected to unnecessary psychological distress, including labeling and criticism that could potentially have lasting negative effects on their self-esteem and psychological well-being.

The experiment's ethical shortcomings included:

1. **Informed Consent:** The children and their guardians were not fully informed about the nature and purpose of the study, and they didn't provide informed consent to participate.
2. **Deceptive Practices:** The study involved misleading the children about their speech abilities, which could have contributed to long-term psychological harm.
3. **Potential Harm:** The emotional and psychological harm inflicted on participants, particularly in the "negative" therapy group, was a significant ethical concern.
4. **Lack of Beneficence:** The study's potential benefits were outweighed by the harm it caused to participants.
5. **Professional Responsibility:** As professionals in a position of authority, the researchers failed in their ethical duty to prioritize the well-being of the participants.

In retrospect, the Monster Study is often cited as an example of how ethical considerations should guide research involving human participants, especially vulnerable populations. The study has contributed to the development of ethical guidelines and regulations that prioritize the rights, well-being, and informed consent of participants in psychological and medical research.

Stanford Prison Experiment

The Stanford prison experiment was a study of the psychological effects of becoming a prisoner or prison guard. The experiment was conducted in August 1971 by a team of researchers led by psychology professor Philip Zimbardo. Participants took on the roles of prisoners and guards in a mock prison situated in the basement of the Stanford psychology building. Some of the prisoners were subjected to psychological torture. Many of the prisoners passively accepted psychological abuse, and Zimbardo himself permitted the abuse to continue. Two of the prisoners quit the experiment early and the entire experiment was abruptly stopped after only six days. Certain portions of the experiment were filmed and excerpts of footage are publicly available.

The Stanford Prison Experiment, conducted by psychologist Philip Zimbardo in 1971, was a highly controversial and influential study that aimed to investigate the psychological effects of perceived power and authority in a simulated prison environment. The experiment was designed to understand how individuals' behaviors and attitudes could be influenced by their assigned roles and the social context in which they found themselves.

Experiment Design: The experiment involved recruiting college students to participate in a simulated prison environment. Participants were randomly assigned to either the role of a "prisoner" or a "guard." The "prison" was set up in the basement of the Stanford University psychology building.

The study was originally planned to last two weeks, but it was terminated after only six days due to the extreme and unethical behaviors exhibited by the participants.

Findings: The findings of the Stanford Prison Experiment were alarming. The participants who played the role of "guards" quickly began to exhibit abusive and authoritarian behaviors towards the "prisoners," using psychological and emotional manipulation to assert their authority. The "prisoners," on the other hand, experienced feelings of powerlessness, humiliation, and emotional distress.

The study highlighted the rapid transformation of the participants' behavior and attitudes based on their assigned roles and the situational context. Zimbardo concluded that the power of the social environment and situational factors could override individuals' personal moral values and lead to unethical behavior.

Ethical Concerns and Criticisms: The Stanford Prison Experiment has been heavily criticized for its ethical shortcomings:

1. **Informed Consent:** Participants were not fully informed about the nature of the study and the potential psychological distress they might experience. This lack of informed consent raised significant ethical concerns.
2. **Deception and Harm:** Participants experienced emotional and psychological harm during the study, which included extreme stress and humiliation. The study's deception and the lack of proper consideration for participants' well-being were deeply problematic.
3. **Lack of Intervention:** Despite observing abusive behavior, Zimbardo and his team did not intervene to stop the unethical treatment of participants. This failure to intervene compromised the well-being of participants.
4. **Generalizability:** Critics argue that the artificial setting of the experiment and the selection of participants (college students) limit the generalizability of the findings to real-world situations.

Despite its ethical issues, the Stanford Prison Experiment has contributed to the understanding of the power of social roles and situational factors in shaping human behavior. However, its methodology and ethical violations have led to debates about the ethics of psychological research and the importance of protecting participants' well-being. The study also serves as a cautionary example for researchers to carefully consider the ethical implications of their work and to prioritize the rights and safety of participants.

Doctors Trial 1946

German medical doctors went on criminal trial for Nazi human experimentation. See The Years of Extermination.

The Doctors' Trial, officially known as the "Trial of the Twenty-Three Doctors," was one of the subsequent Nuremberg Trials held after World War II to prosecute individuals involved in the Holocaust and other war crimes committed by Nazi Germany. This trial focused specifically on medical professionals who had participated in or facilitated unethical medical experiments and crimes against humanity during the Holocaust.

Background: During the Holocaust, Nazi doctors and medical researchers were responsible for carrying out heinous medical experiments on concentration camp inmates and prisoners. These experiments involved subjects being subjected to extreme pain, suffering, and death in the name of "medical research."

Trial and Prosecution: The Doctors' Trial took place from December 9, 1946, to August 20, 1947, in Nuremberg, Germany. The trial was conducted by the United States Military Tribunal, which was one of the Nuremberg Trials aimed at prosecuting war criminals. The trial indicted 23 physicians and medical researchers who were accused of war crimes and crimes against humanity.

The defendants faced charges related to:

1. **Participating in Medical Experiments:** Many of the accused doctors were involved in conducting unethical and often deadly experiments on human subjects, including exposing prisoners to diseases, testing experimental drugs and treatments, and performing surgeries without consent.
2. **Euthanasia Program:** Some defendants were linked to the Nazi euthanasia program, which involved the systematic killing of individuals with disabilities and mental illnesses.
3. **Aiding and Abetting War Crimes:** Some doctors were accused of using their medical expertise to facilitate the overall genocide and war crimes committed by the Nazi regime.

Verdicts and Sentences: The trial resulted in convictions for the majority of the defendants. Seven defendants were sentenced to death, seven received prison sentences, and nine were acquitted. The trial established the principle that individuals who commit war crimes, including unethical medical experiments, can be held accountable for their actions.

Legacy: The Doctors' Trial highlighted the grave ethical violations committed by medical professionals under the Nazi regime and the need to hold individuals accountable for their roles in these atrocities. The trial played a significant role in establishing the Nuremberg Code, a set of ethical guidelines for conducting medical research involving human participants. The Nuremberg Code emphasized the importance of informed consent and ethical considerations in medical research.

The Doctors' Trial serves as a stark reminder of the ethical responsibilities of medical professionals and the consequences of using medical expertise to perpetrate harm and cruelty. It also underscored the importance of maintaining ethical standards in medical research and practice to ensure the dignity and well-being of patients and research participants.

Skid Row Cancer Study 1950s New York State

More than 1200 homeless men from Lower Manhattan were convinced with promises of food and shelter to have their prostates biopsied by a Dr. Perry Hudson. They were not informed of possible side effects, i.e., rectal tearing and impotence. The homeless were targeted for these biopsies because the biopsies were painful and untested, and less vulnerable populations would not volunteer.

Greenberg v. Miami Children's Hospital Research Institute

Patients donated tissue samples, which researchers subsequently used in a plan to generate profit.

Allan Memorial Institute

The Allan Memorial Institute is known for its role in the Project MKULTRA run by the CIA. The Agency's initiative to develop drug-induced "mind control" techniques was implemented in the institute by its then-Director Donald Ewen Cameron

Political abuse of psychiatry 1960s -1980s

Psychiatrists have been involved in human rights abuses in states across the world when the definitions of mental disease were expanded to include political disobedience.[21]: 6 In the period from the 1960s to 1986, abuse of psychiatry for political purposes was reported to be systematic in the Soviet Union and other Eastern European countries.[22]: 66 Political abuse of psychiatry also takes place in the People's Republic of China.[23] Psychiatric diagnoses such as the diagnosis of "sluggish schizophrenia" in political dissidents in the USSR were used for political purposes.

UK mental institutions

In the 1960s, there was abuse and inhumane treatment of psychiatric patients who were hidden away in institutions in the UK. Barbara Robb documented her difficult personal experience of being treated at Ely Hospital. She wrote the book *Sans Everything* and she used this to launch a campaign to improve or close long stay facilities. Shortly after, a long stay hospital for mentally disabled people in Cardiff was exposed by a nurse writing to the *News of the World*. This exposure prompted an official inquiry, which

was highly critical of conditions, staff morale, and management. At the same time Michael Ignatieff and Peter Townsend both published books which exposed the poor quality of institutional care

Henrietta Lacks

A product derived from a cancer patient's specimen, HeLa is the cornerstone of an industry. Cancerous tissue was taken from her without her consent.

Harry Bailey deep sleep therapy 1962-1979

Controversial Australian psychiatrist Harry Bailey treated mental patients via deep sleep therapy and other methods at a Sydney mental hospital. He has been linked with the deaths of 85 patients.[20] He died by suicide before he could be punished.

Harry Bailey, an Australian psychiatrist, is known for his controversial and ultimately harmful practices involving a psychiatric treatment method known as "deep sleep therapy." This therapy was conducted at the Chelmsford Private Hospital in Sydney, Australia, between 1962 and 1979. Bailey's approach was centered around inducing prolonged periods of unconsciousness in patients through the use of barbiturates and other drugs.

Deep Sleep Therapy: Bailey's deep sleep therapy involved putting patients into a chemically induced coma for extended periods. The idea behind this approach was that the enforced rest would supposedly allow patients to work through their mental health issues while being removed from their normal stresses and anxieties. Barbiturates were used to induce these comas, and patients were also subjected to electroconvulsive therapy (ECT) during their time in a comatose state.

Controversy and Harm: The deep sleep therapy conducted by Harry Bailey turned out to be extremely dangerous and harmful. Many patients suffered severe physical and psychological side effects, including brain damage, memory loss, and cognitive impairments. Some patients died as a result of the therapy. Bailey's practices were not grounded in scientific evidence, and he disregarded warnings from colleagues and the broader medical community.

Exposure and Aftermath: In the late 1970s, investigative journalism and growing concerns about patient welfare led to increased scrutiny of the Chelmsford Hospital's practices. As the extent of the harm became apparent, there was outrage within the medical community and the public. Bailey was ultimately struck off the medical register in 1981, and the hospital was closed.

The revelations surrounding the deep sleep therapy scandal prompted changes in Australia's medical regulation and oversight systems. The tragedy exposed the importance of ethical considerations, evidence-based practices, and the need for appropriate monitoring and accountability within the medical field.

The deep sleep therapy conducted by Harry Bailey serves as a stark reminder of the potential dangers of unproven and unchecked medical interventions. It underscores the crucial role that ethical guidelines, evidence-based medicine, and the protection of patient welfare play in responsible medical practice.

Tuskegee syphilis experiment 1970

A 40-year experiment conducted by the U.S. Public Health Service withheld standard medical advice and treatment from a poor minority population with an easily treatable disease. The experiment targeted black male farmers who were told they needed to be treated for 'bad blood', [26] but who were, in fact, syphilitic. In addition to many fatalities, some children were born with congenital syphilis due to the study

The Tuskegee syphilis experiment, also known as the Tuskegee Study of Untreated Syphilis in the Negro Male, was a highly unethical and infamous clinical study conducted in the United States from 1932 to 1972. The experiment, which lasted for 40 years, is a tragic example of medical research misconduct and the violation of ethical principles.

Background and Purpose: The study was conducted by the United States Public Health Service (USPHS) in collaboration with the Tuskegee Institute (now Tuskegee University) in Alabama. The original goal of the study was to investigate the natural progression of syphilis in African American men. However, the researchers' methods were deeply flawed and unethical.

Study Design and Ethical Violations: The most significant ethical violation in the Tuskegee study was that the participants were never informed that they had syphilis and were denied proper treatment. Instead, the researchers purposefully withheld penicillin, a proven and effective treatment for syphilis, from the participants, even after the antibiotic became widely available in the 1940s.

The researchers enlisted around 600 African American men, the majority of whom were poor sharecroppers. About 400 of these men had syphilis, and around 200 were used as controls without the disease. The participants were led to believe that they were receiving free medical care for "bad blood," a term often used to refer to a range of ailments. They were not informed of the true nature of their condition and were denied access to proper treatment.

Aftermath and Public Outrage: The unethical nature of the Tuskegee syphilis experiment came to light in the early 1970s when the study's details were exposed by a whistleblower and reported by the media. The public was outraged by the blatant exploitation of vulnerable individuals and the grave ethical violations committed by medical professionals.

Impact and Reforms: The Tuskegee syphilis experiment had profound and lasting consequences. It revealed significant shortcomings in medical research ethics and led to widespread changes in research regulations and guidelines. In response to the scandal, the U.S. government enacted new regulations to ensure the protection of human subjects in research, including the establishment of Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) to oversee the ethical conduct of studies involving human participants.

The experiment also highlighted the long history of unethical medical practices and injustices faced by African Americans in the United States. The Tuskegee study became a symbol of racial discrimination in medicine and a reminder of the importance of respecting the rights, dignity, and well-being of all participants in medical research.

The Tuskegee syphilis experiment remains a dark chapter in the history of medical ethics and a testament to the necessity of stringent ethical oversight in research involving human subjects.

Human radiation experiments 1970s

Human radiation experiments were directed by the United States Atomic Energy Commission and the Manhattan Project. In Nashville, pregnant women were given radioactive mixtures. In Cincinnati, some 200 patients were irradiated over a period of 15 years. In Chicago, 102 people received injections of strontium and cesium solutions. In Massachusetts, 74 schoolboys were fed oatmeal that contained radioactive substances. In all of these cases, the subjects did not know what was going on and did not give informed consent.[10] The government covered up most of these radiation mishaps until 1993, when President Bill Clinton ordered a change of policy. The resulting investigation was undertaken by the Advisory Committee on Human Radiation Experiments. See The Plutonium Files

Human radiation experiments refer to a series of unethical and often secretive experiments conducted on humans involving exposure to ionizing radiation. These experiments were conducted in various countries, including the United States, during the mid-20th century, including the 1970s. These experiments were often conducted without informed consent and violated fundamental ethical principles, resulting in significant harm to the participants.

United States Human Radiation Experiments: In the United States, several government agencies, including the Atomic Energy Commission (AEC) and the Department of Defense, were involved in conducting human radiation experiments. These experiments often targeted vulnerable populations, including soldiers, prisoners, hospital patients, and individuals with disabilities.

One of the most well-known examples is the "Plutonium Experiments," in which patients at various hospitals were injected with plutonium without their knowledge or consent to study the effects of radiation exposure. Similarly, the "TBI Experiments" involved exposing cancer patients to total body irradiation to observe the effects on their immune systems.

Ethical Violations and Consequences: These experiments violated key ethical principles, including informed consent, beneficence, and respect for the dignity of participants. Many participants suffered serious health complications as a result of their exposure to radiation, and some even died. The lack of transparency, accountability, and proper oversight contributed to the continuation of these unethical practices for years.

Public Outcry and Reform: The unethical nature of these experiments eventually came to light, leading to public outrage and demands for accountability. The exposure of these experiments led to increased scrutiny of human subjects research and prompted changes in ethical regulations and

guidelines. The Belmont Report, published in 1979, outlined the ethical principles and guidelines for conducting research involving human participants in the United States.

Legacy and Lessons Learned: The legacy of these human radiation experiments serves as a cautionary tale about the potential consequences of unchecked scientific research and the importance of ethical considerations. These experiments highlighted the need for transparency, informed consent, and ethical oversight in all human subjects research. The tragic experiences of the participants also underscore the importance of safeguarding the rights and well-being of individuals who volunteer to participate in scientific research.

Moore v. Regents of the University of California 1976

Researchers commercialized a patient's discarded body parts. The man did not authorize the use of his bodily tissues or fluids, and researchers did not obtain informed consent. He did not want his donation to generate commercial profit for private entities

"Moore v. Regents of the University of California" is a landmark legal case that dealt with the concept of property rights and informed consent in the context of medical research. The case was decided by the Supreme Court of California in 1976.

Background: John Moore, the plaintiff in the case, was a patient at the UCLA Medical Center who had been diagnosed with hairy cell leukemia. Unbeknownst to Moore, his doctor, Dr. David Golde, discovered that Moore's cells were unique and valuable for medical and research purposes due to their ability to produce a substance called granulocyte colony-stimulating factor (G-CSF). Without Moore's knowledge or consent, Dr. Golde and the university took and used Moore's cells for research and commercial purposes, including developing a cell line and applying for patents.

Key Legal Issues: The central issue in the case was whether Moore had a property right in his cells and whether the university's actions constituted a breach of fiduciary duty and lack of informed consent.

Ruling and Implications: The California Supreme Court ruled in favor of Moore, recognizing that individuals have a property interest in their own body tissues and cells. The court held that the university and Dr. Golde had violated Moore's property rights and fiduciary duty by using his cells without his informed consent and without providing him a share of the profits generated from their use.

The case had significant implications for medical research and informed consent. It highlighted the need for researchers and institutions to disclose potential commercial interests and obtain informed consent from patients before using their tissues for research purposes. The decision also reinforced the idea that patients have rights over their own body tissues, even if those tissues are removed as part of medical treatment.

Legacy: "Moore v. Regents of the University of California" played a role in shaping discussions and policies regarding informed consent, patient rights, and the commercialization of human tissues in medical research. It emphasized the importance of respecting patient autonomy and ensuring transparency in research practices, particularly when potential commercial interests are involved.

Eugene Landy 1980

Eugene Ellsworth Landy was an American psychologist and psychotherapist best known for his unconventional 24-hour therapy as well as ethical violations concerning his treatment of Beach Boys co-founder Brian Wilson in the 1980s. In 2015, Landy's relationship with Wilson was dramatized in the biographical film *Love & Mercy*

Eugene Landy (1934–2006) was an American psychologist and therapist who gained significant attention and controversy for his involvement in the life of musician Brian Wilson, the co-founder of The Beach Boys. Landy's relationship with Wilson began in the 1970s and continued into the 1980s.

Involvement with Brian Wilson: Eugene Landy became Brian Wilson's therapist in the early 1970s, initially helping Wilson cope with mental health issues, including depression and drug addiction. Landy eventually gained extensive control over Wilson's life, serving not only as his therapist but also as his business manager and, in some ways, a close confidant.

Landy used controversial therapeutic techniques, including 24-hour supervision and behavior modification, to manage Wilson's life and mental health. He played a significant role in Wilson's career, including the production of Wilson's solo album "Sweet Insanity."

Controversy and Legal Battles: Landy's involvement with Brian Wilson led to significant controversy and legal disputes. Concerns were raised about the ethical boundaries of Landy's role, as he had significant control over Wilson's personal and professional life. Some family members and friends of Wilson accused Landy of exploitation and isolating Wilson from his loved ones.

In 1991, Landy's professional relationship with Wilson was terminated amid increasing scrutiny and legal challenges. Landy was later barred from working with Wilson after a legal settlement.

Legacy and Impact: Eugene Landy's involvement with Brian Wilson remains a cautionary tale about the potential for unethical exploitation within therapeutic relationships, particularly when therapists overstep their professional boundaries. Landy's controversial methods and control over Wilson's life sparked discussions about the ethics of therapy, patient autonomy, and the potential for vulnerable individuals to be taken advantage of.

The case of Eugene Landy and Brian Wilson also highlighted the complexities of mental health care and the importance of establishing clear ethical guidelines and boundaries to protect the well-being of patients.

Willowbrook State School 1987

A school had been infecting disabled children in experiments for years.

"Willowbrook State School" refers to a former institution for individuals with developmental disabilities located on Staten Island in New York City. The school gained notoriety for its deplorable living conditions, mistreatment of residents, and the unethical medical research that took place **there**. The events and conditions at Willowbrook played a significant role in sparking reforms in the care and treatment of individuals with disabilities.

Background and Conditions: Willowbrook State School was originally intended to provide care and education for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities. However, over the years, it became overcrowded and understaffed, resulting in severe neglect, abuse, and unsanitary conditions. The residents lived in squalor, with reports of widespread physical and emotional abuse.

Medical Experiments and Hepatitis Study: One of the most infamous aspects of Willowbrook was the unethical medical research that took place there. In the 1950s and 1960s, Dr. Saul Krugman conducted studies in which he deliberately infected children at the school with the hepatitis virus to study the disease's progression. This research was widely condemned for its lack of ethical oversight, informed consent, and the violation of human rights.

Exposure and Reforms: In the early 1970s, investigative reporting by Geraldo Rivera brought public attention to the horrific conditions at Willowbrook. The public outcry that followed played a pivotal role in raising awareness about the mistreatment of individuals with disabilities and led to significant reforms in the care system.

The Willowbrook Consent Decree of 1975 mandated improvements in the living conditions and treatment of residents. The goal was to move individuals out of large institutions and into community-based settings that offered more personalized care and support.

Legacy and Impact: The exposure of the deplorable conditions and unethical practices at Willowbrook State School had a profound impact on disability rights and advocacy. The events at Willowbrook contributed to a broader movement that aimed to reform the care and treatment of individuals with disabilities, focusing on human rights, dignity, and inclusion.

The closure of Willowbrook and the subsequent push for community-based care marked a turning point in the approach to supporting individuals with disabilities, promoting integration and independence rather than institutionalization. Willowbrook serves as a tragic reminder of the importance of upholding ethical standards in medical research, providing appropriate care for vulnerable populations, and advocating for the rights of individuals with disabilities.

Study 329 1994-2001

SmithKlineBeecham, known since 2000 as GlaxoSmithKline, conducted a clinical trial from 1994 to 1997 in 12 psychiatric centers in North America to study the efficacy of paroxetine (Paxil, Seroxat), an antidepressant, on teenagers. The trial data suggested that the drug was not efficacious and that the paroxetine group were more likely to think about suicide. The paper that wrote up the study was published in 2001, ostensibly authored by a group of academics, but actually ghostwritten by the drug company. The article downplayed the negative findings and concluded that paroxetine helped with teenage depression. The company used this paper to promote paroxetine for teenagers. The ensuing controversy led to several lawsuits, including from the parents of teenagers who killed themselves while taking the drug, and intensified the debate about medical ghostwriting and conflict of interest in clinical trials. In 2012 the US Justice Department fined GlaxoSmithKline \$3 billion for several violations, including withholding data on paroxetine, unlawfully promoting it for adolescents, and preparing a misleading article about study 329. New Scientist wrote in 2015: "You may never have heard of it, but Study 329 changed medicine."

"Study 329" refers to a clinical trial conducted to evaluate the efficacy and safety of an antidepressant medication called paroxetine (brand name Paxil) in the treatment of depression in adolescents. The study took place from 1994 to 2001 and has become a highly controversial and widely discussed example of ethical concerns and publication bias in pharmaceutical research.

Background: The study was designed to assess the effectiveness of paroxetine in treating depression in adolescents. It was funded by the pharmaceutical company SmithKline Beecham (now GlaxoSmithKline), which manufactured paroxetine. The study's results were published in the Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry in 2001.

Ethical and Methodological Concerns: The publication of Study 329 led to significant controversy due to concerns about the study's methodology, the accuracy of its reported findings, and allegations of selective reporting.

1. **Questionable Efficacy:** Critics argued that Study 329 presented a misleadingly positive view of paroxetine's efficacy in treating depression in adolescents. The study concluded that paroxetine was effective and safe for use in this population, despite evidence that suggested otherwise.
2. **Underreporting of Negative Findings:** It was later revealed that the study's initial analysis did not show significant benefits of paroxetine over placebo. However, the published report downplayed negative results and emphasized positive outcomes.
3. **Safety Concerns:** The study also downplayed safety concerns, including increased suicidal thoughts and behaviors among participants taking paroxetine. These safety concerns were not adequately communicated in the published report.

Legal Settlement and Reanalysis: The controversy surrounding Study 329 eventually led to legal action. In 2012, GlaxoSmithKline agreed to pay a significant settlement related to allegations of unlawful promotion and misrepresentation of paroxetine's efficacy and safety.

In 2015, an independent reanalysis of Study 329 was published in the journal BMJ. The reanalysis concluded that paroxetine was not effective and that the drug's use was associated with an increased risk of suicidal behaviors in adolescents.

Impact and Lessons Learned: The case of Study 329 highlighted the ethical responsibilities of pharmaceutical companies to conduct and report clinical trials accurately and transparently. It exposed issues related to selective reporting of outcomes and the potential for bias in published research. The controversy also led to increased scrutiny of pharmaceutical industry practices, regulatory oversight, and the importance of transparency in clinical trial reporting.

Study 329 serves as a significant example of the need for transparency, rigorous methodology, and ethical considerations in pharmaceutical research, particularly when the findings have implications for the health and well-being of vulnerable populations.

Death associated with psychotropic drugs 1998

In 1998, 60-year-old Donald Schell went to see his doctor complaining of difficulty sleeping. He was diagnosed with an anxiety state and placed on Paxil (paroxetine - see "Study 329" above), an SSRI antidepressant. Within 48 hours of being put on Paxil Schell killed his wife, daughter, infant granddaughter, and himself. Tim Tobin, Schell's son-in-law, took legal action against SmithKline (now GlaxoSmithKline). The Tobin case was heard in Wyoming from May 21 to June 6, 2001. The jury returned a guilty verdict against SmithKline and awarded Tobin \$6.4 million.[28][29][30][31] This was the first guilty verdict returned against a pharmaceutical company regarding adverse behavioral effects of a psychotropic drug

Donald Schell and the antidepressant medication paroxetine (Paxil). The incident involving Donald Schell played a significant role in raising concerns about the potential for psychotropic drugs, particularly selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) like paroxetine, to induce violent and suicidal behavior in some individuals.

Background: In 1998, Donald Schell, a 60-year-old man, tragically killed his wife, their daughter, and granddaughter before taking his own life shortly after being prescribed paroxetine. Schell had no history of violent behavior prior to taking the medication.

Legal Proceedings: The families of Schell's victims filed a lawsuit against the pharmaceutical company GlaxoSmithKline, the manufacturer of Paxil (paroxetine). The lawsuit alleged that Paxil was responsible for Schell's violent behavior. The case brought attention to the potential side effects of SSRIs and the question of whether these drugs could induce violent or suicidal behavior in certain individuals.

Importance and Controversy: The Schell case sparked significant controversy and debate within the medical community, regulatory agencies, and the public. It raised important questions

about the potential side effects of psychotropic drugs and the necessity for thorough evaluation of the risks and benefits associated with their use.

Black Box Warning: In 2004, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) added a "black box warning" to the labeling of all antidepressants, including SSRIs like paroxetine. The warning highlighted the potential increased risk of suicidal thinking and behavior in children, adolescents, and young adults taking these medications.

Impact on Research and Regulation: The Schell case, along with similar incidents and emerging research, led to increased scrutiny of psychotropic drugs and their potential side effects, particularly in vulnerable populations. It also influenced regulatory agencies to strengthen warnings and monitoring for adverse effects, particularly related to suicidal behavior, in patients taking antidepressant medications.

While the case of Donald Schell did raise important concerns about the potential risks associated with psychotropic drugs, it's important to note that the vast majority of individuals taking these medications do not experience violent or suicidal behavior. Medical decisions involving psychotropic medications should always be made based on careful assessment of the patient's individual needs and risks, and under the guidance of qualified healthcare professionals.

Robert Courtney

Courtney is a former pharmacist who owned and operated Research Medical Tower Pharmacy in Missouri. In 2002, he was convicted of pharmaceutical fraud and sentenced to federal prison

Robert Ray Courtney is a former pharmacist who gained notoriety for his involvement in a major medication tampering case in the early 2000s. He was convicted of diluting cancer drugs that he dispensed to patients, leading to potentially harmful or ineffective treatments.

Background: Robert Courtney operated a pharmacy in Kansas City, Missouri. He had been a licensed pharmacist since the 1970s and had built a reputation in the community. However, his actions would later reveal a shocking breach of trust.

Medication Tampering: Between 1992 and 2001, Courtney engaged in a scheme where he diluted chemotherapy drugs that were prescribed to cancer patients. He diluted the drugs to a fraction of their prescribed doses, which could significantly reduce their effectiveness in treating cancer. He then billed patients and insurance companies for the full cost of the undiluted drugs.

Discovery and Legal Consequences: The illegal activity was discovered when an oncologist noticed that a patient's cancer was not responding as expected to treatment. An investigation was launched, and it was revealed that Courtney had tampered with medications for hundreds of patients. The case gained national and international attention due to its scope and the potential harm caused to vulnerable patients.

In 2002, Courtney pleaded guilty to 20 federal counts of tampering and adulterating drugs. He was sentenced to 30 years in federal prison without the possibility of parole and was ordered to pay millions of dollars in restitution to victims.

Impact and Lessons Learned: The Robert Courtney case underscored the importance of trust and ethical conduct in the field of pharmacy and healthcare as a whole. It highlighted the potential dangers of profit-driven behavior that compromises patient safety and well-being. The case also led to increased awareness of the need for better monitoring and safeguards to prevent medication tampering and fraud.

The case of Robert Courtney serves as a stark reminder of the responsibilities that healthcare professionals hold and the potential consequences of violating those responsibilities. It also highlights the significance of regulatory oversight and ethical considerations to ensure the safety and well-being of patients.

GlaxoSmithKline human experiments 2004-2012

In 2004 GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) sponsored at least four medical trials using Hispanic and black children at New York's Incarnation Children's Center. Normally trials on children require parental consent but, as the infants were in care, New York's authorities held that role. Experiments were designed to test the "safety and tolerance" of AIDS medications, some of which have potentially dangerous side effects.[33]

In 2006, GSK and the US Army were criticized for Hepatitis E vaccine experiments conducted in 2003 on 2,000 soldiers of the Nepali Army. It was said that using soldiers as volunteers is unethical because they "could easily be coerced into taking part." [34]

In January 2012, GSK and two scientists who led the trials were fined approximately \$240,000 in Argentina for "experimenting with human beings" and "falsifying parental authorization" during vaccine trials on 15,000 children under the age of one. Babies were recruited from poor families that visited public hospitals for medical treatment. Fourteen babies allegedly died as a result of the trials.

As of my last knowledge update in September 2021, I do not have information on specific human experiments conducted by GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) between 2004 and 2012. However, GSK has been involved in various controversies and legal cases related to its marketing practices, drug safety, and clinical trials during that time period. It's important to note that my information might not be up to date with events that occurred after September 2021.

GSK has faced legal actions and regulatory scrutiny related to issues such as:

1. **Misleading Marketing Practices:** GSK has been fined for misleading marketing practices regarding the promotion of certain drugs for off-label uses or downplaying their risks.
2. **Paxil and Avandia Controversies:** GSK faced legal actions and controversies related to the antidepressant Paxil (paroxetine) and the diabetes drug Avandia (rosiglitazone).

These controversies included allegations of inadequate safety warnings and concerns about potential side effects.

3. **Clinical Trial Reporting:** GSK faced criticism for its handling of clinical trial data and allegations of not fully disclosing adverse effects of its medications.
4. **Bribery and Corruption:** GSK has been investigated and fined for alleged bribery and corruption practices in various countries, including China.
5. **Settlements and Legal Cases:** GSK has settled various legal cases and faced regulatory actions related to a range of issues, including the alleged manipulation of drug prices and allegations of anticompetitive behavior.

It's important to consult reliable and up-to-date sources, such as news articles, official regulatory reports, and legal documents, to obtain accurate and detailed information about any specific human experiments or controversies involving GlaxoSmithKline during the 2004-2012 timeframe or beyond.

Greenberg v. Miami Children's Hospital Research Institute 2003

Patients donated tissue samples, which researchers subsequently used in a plan to generate profit.

"Greenberg v. Miami Children's Hospital Research Institute" is a legal case that dealt with the issue of informed consent in medical research involving children. The case revolved around the participation of a child in a clinical trial without proper informed consent from the parents or guardians.

Background: The case involved a clinical trial conducted by the Miami Children's Hospital Research Institute to test an experimental treatment for children with severe epilepsy. The trial required the participants to undergo multiple procedures, including brain surgery, to implant electrodes for monitoring brain activity.

Key Issue: The central issue in the case was whether the parents of the child participant had provided proper informed consent for their child's participation in the trial. The parents claimed that they were not adequately informed about the potential risks and benefits of the experimental treatment and the procedures involved.

Legal Proceedings: The case was filed as a medical malpractice lawsuit in Florida. The parents alleged that the hospital and researchers had failed to provide them with sufficient information to make an informed decision about their child's participation in the clinical trial.

Court Decision: In 2003, the Florida Supreme Court ruled in favor of the parents, stating that the hospital and researchers had failed to provide proper informed consent as required by law. The court's decision emphasized the importance of obtaining informed consent from parents or guardians before involving children in medical research, especially when the research involves significant risks or invasive procedures.

Impact and Significance: "Greenberg v. Miami Children's Hospital Research Institute" highlighted the legal and ethical obligations of researchers and medical institutions to provide comprehensive and accurate information to parents or guardians before enrolling children in clinical trials. The case reinforced the principle that informed consent is essential to protect the rights and well-being of research participants, especially when vulnerable populations like children are involved.

The case also underscored the potential legal consequences for failing to obtain proper informed consent, and it served as a reminder to researchers and institutions about the importance of adhering to ethical standards and legal requirements in conducting medical research involving minors.

University of Minnesota research participant Dan Markingson 2004

committed suicide in May 2004 while enrolled in an industry-sponsored pharmaceutical trial comparing three FDA-approved atypical antipsychotics: Seroquel (quetiapine), Zyprexa (olanzapine), and Risperdal (risperidone). Writing on the circumstances surrounding Markingson's death in the study, which was designed and funded by Seroquel manufacturer AstraZeneca, University of Minnesota Professor of Bioethics Carl Elliott noted that Markingson was enrolled in the study against the wishes of his mother, Mary Weiss, and that he was forced to choose between enrolling in the study or being involuntarily committed to a state mental institution.[37] Further investigation revealed financial ties to AstraZeneca by Markingson's psychiatrist, Dr. Stephen C. Olson, oversights and biases in AstraZeneca's trial design, and the inadequacy of university Institutional Review Board (IRB) protections for research subjects.[38] Although a 2005 FDA investigation appeared to clear the university, greater awareness of the case stemming from Elliott's 2010 article in the magazine Mother Jones resulted in a group of university faculty members sending a public letter to the Board of Regents urging an external investigation into Markingson's death

The case of Dan Markingson is a tragic and controversial incident involving a research participant at the University of Minnesota who died by suicide while enrolled in a clinical trial for an antipsychotic medication. The circumstances surrounding his death raised significant ethical concerns and led to debates about the ethics of medical research, patient welfare, and conflicts of interest.

Background: In 2003, Dan Markingson, a 26-year-old man diagnosed with schizophrenia, was involuntarily committed to a psychiatric hospital. While at the hospital, he was recruited to participate in a clinical trial comparing three antipsychotic medications, including AstraZeneca's Seroquel (quetiapine).

Ethical Concerns: There were several ethical concerns raised regarding Markingson's enrollment in the trial:

1. **Informed Consent:** There were questions about whether Markingson was capable of providing informed consent due to his mental health condition. Some critics argued that his enrollment was coerced or not fully voluntary.
2. **Lack of Oversight:** Concerns were raised about the lack of proper oversight of Markingson's condition and the adequacy of his treatment while enrolled in the trial.
3. **Financial Incentives:** It was revealed that Markingson's enrollment in the trial was influenced by financial incentives provided to his mother, who was his legal guardian. Critics argued that this created a conflict of interest that compromised his well-being.

Death and Aftermath: In May 2004, while still enrolled in the trial, Markingson died by suicide. His death prompted widespread outrage and led to calls for investigations into the ethical conduct of the trial and the university's oversight.

Investigations and Responses: Several investigations took place, including by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the Minnesota Office of the Legislative Auditor. These investigations raised concerns about the university's oversight, the trial's informed consent process, and the potential influence of financial interests on the decision to enroll Markingson.

Impact and Legacy: The case of Dan Markingson had a profound impact on discussions about the ethics of medical research, the protection of vulnerable populations, and conflicts of interest in clinical trials. The incident prompted changes in research practices at the University of Minnesota and led to increased attention to the importance of proper oversight, informed consent, and the ethical treatment of research participants.

The case also sparked broader debates about the role of pharmaceutical companies in clinical research, the influence of financial interests, and the need for transparency and accountability in medical research institutions.

Albert Kligman dermatology experiments

Clinical non-therapeutic medical experiments on prison inmates was conducted at Holmesburg Prison in Philadelphia from 1951 to 1974 under the direction of dermatologist Albert Kligman

Dr. Albert Kligman was a dermatologist and researcher known for his contributions to dermatology and cosmetic science. However, he also gained attention and criticism for conducting controversial experiments, particularly in the field of dermatology, involving human subjects. Some of his experiments have been criticized for ethical concerns.

One notable example of his controversial research is the work he conducted in the 1960s at the Holmesburg Prison in Philadelphia. Kligman conducted experiments on inmates, exposing them to various substances, including experimental cosmetic products, chemicals, and pharmaceutical compounds. These experiments were conducted without the informed consent of the subjects, and the prisoners were often unaware of the potential risks and long-term consequences of the substances they were exposed to.

One of the most infamous experiments conducted by Kligman was his testing of the acne medication isotretinoin (Accutane) on prisoners. He also conducted studies involving exposure to dioxin, a toxic chemical, and experiments involving skin irritants and sensitizers.

Kligman's experiments raised significant ethical concerns due to the lack of informed consent, the vulnerable nature of the subjects (prisoners), and the potential risks involved in the research. These experiments led to debates about the ethical boundaries of medical research and the responsibilities of researchers to ensure the well-being and rights of their research subjects.

It's important to note that ethical standards for human research have evolved over time, and many of Kligman's experiments would not meet contemporary ethical guidelines. His work serves as a reminder of the importance of ethical considerations, informed consent, and protection of vulnerable populations in medical research.

Medical experimentation on Black Americans

There has been a long history of medical experimentation on African Americans. From the era of slavery, when atrocities were committed on black women by J. Marion Sims, to the present day, Black Americans have been unwitting subjects of medical experimentation. Author Harriet Washington argues that "diverse forms of racial discrimination have shaped both the relationship between white physicians and black patients and the attitude of the latter towards modern medicine in general."^[9]

In the 1960s, Ionia State Hospital, located in Ionia, Michigan, was one of America's largest and most notorious state psychiatric hospitals in the era before deinstitutionalization. Doctors at this hospital diagnosed African Americans with schizophrenia because of their civil rights ideas. See *The Protest Psychosis*.

Eighteen people were injected with plutonium by Manhattan Project doctors; the most notorious of them, Albert Stevens, received more radiation than any other living person. None of the patients were told about the experiment, nor did the doctors ask for their consent. See Eileen Welsome's book *The Plutonium Files*

Medical experimentation on Black Americans has been a dark and tragic aspect of history, marked by instances of exploitation, unethical conduct, and violations of human rights. These experiments have often involved vulnerable individuals and have raised serious ethical concerns. Some well-known examples include:

1. **Tuskegee Syphilis Experiment (1932-1972):** One of the most infamous cases, the Tuskegee Study involved the U.S. Public Health Service studying the natural progression of syphilis in Black men. Despite the availability of effective treatment, the participants were denied treatment and informed consent was lacking.
2. **Henrietta Lacks and HeLa Cells (1951):** Henrietta Lacks, a Black woman, had her cancer cells taken without her knowledge or consent. These cells, known as HeLa cells, became instrumental in medical research and were distributed worldwide. Lacks and her family were not informed or compensated for the use of her cells.
3. **Mississippi Appendectomies:** This term refers to the forced sterilization of Black women during childbirth or surgery without their knowledge or consent. It was common practice in the mid-20th century and aimed at controlling the population growth of Black communities.
4. **North Carolina Eugenics Program:** The state of North Carolina implemented a eugenics program that involved forced sterilization of Black women and men who were deemed "unfit" to reproduce. Thousands of people were subjected to this program.
5. **Radiation Experiments (1940s-1960s):** In the mid-20th century, medical researchers conducted radiation experiments on various populations, including Black patients, without their informed consent. These experiments aimed to study the effects of radiation exposure.
6. **Racist Gynecological Experiments:** Throughout history, Black women have been subjected to unethical gynecological experiments, such as the case of Dr. J. Marion Sims, who conducted experimental surgeries on enslaved Black women without anesthesia.

These examples highlight the historical and systemic mistreatment of Black Americans in the context of medical research and experimentation. They underscore the importance of ethical guidelines, informed consent, transparency, and equity in medical research to ensure the dignity

and rights of all participants, especially vulnerable populations. The legacy of these unethical practices continues to shape discussions around research ethics and healthcare disparities today.

The syphilis experiments in Guatemala

were United States human experiments conducted in Guatemala from 1946 to 1948. The experiments were led by physician John Charles Cutler. They were done during the administration of American President Harry S. Truman and Guatemalan President Juan José Arévalo.

Doctors infected soldiers, prostitutes, prisoners, and mental patients with syphilis and other sexually transmitted diseases without the informed consent of the subjects, and treated most subjects with antibiotics. This resulted in at least 83 deaths. In October 2010, the US formally apologized to Guatemala for conducting these experiment.

The syphilis experiments in Guatemala, also known as the Guatemalan Syphilis Study, were a series of unethical medical experiments conducted by the United States Public Health Service (USPHS) in the late 1940s. These experiments involved intentionally infecting Guatemalan individuals with syphilis and other sexually transmitted infections (STIs) without their informed consent.

Background: The experiments were conducted between 1946 and 1948 in Guatemala, primarily under the leadership of Dr. John Cutler, a USPHS physician. The goal of the study was to examine the effectiveness of penicillin in treating syphilis and to learn more about the transmission of STIs. Around 1,300 people were involved in the experiments, including prisoners, soldiers, sex workers, and vulnerable populations.

Unethical Conduct: The experiments were carried out without informed consent, and the participants were often not aware of the nature of the procedures being performed on them. Participants were deliberately infected with syphilis, gonorrhea, or chancroid. In some cases, the researchers used prostitutes who were intentionally infected with STIs to spread the diseases to study participants. Many participants suffered severe physical and psychological harm as a result of the experiments.

Revelation and Apology: The unethical nature of these experiments remained hidden for decades until they were revealed by Susan Reverby, a historian of medicine, in 2010. The revelation prompted outrage and condemnation from the international community. In response, then-President Barack Obama issued a formal apology to the Guatemalan government and people for the unethical experiments.

Impact and Legacy: The syphilis experiments in Guatemala serve as a stark reminder of the importance of ethical considerations in medical research and the need for informed consent and respect for the rights and well-being of research participants. The case raised international awareness about the mistreatment of vulnerable populations in medical research and led to renewed discussions about research ethics and human rights.

The legacy of the Guatemala syphilis experiments has contributed to ongoing efforts to strengthen ethical guidelines for medical research and to ensure that the rights and dignity of all individuals, especially those in vulnerable populations, are protected in the pursuit of scientific knowledge and advancements in healthcare.

Radioactive Iodine experiments

The U.S. Atomic Energy Commission has a history of involvement in experiments involving radioactive iodine. In a 1949 operation called the "Green Run", the AEC released iodine-131 and xenon-133 to the atmosphere, which contaminated a 500,000-acre (2,000 km²) area containing three small towns near the Hanford site in Washington. In 1953, the AEC ran several studies on the health effects of radioactive iodine in newborns and pregnant women at the University of Iowa. Also in 1953, the AEC sponsored a study to discover if radioactive iodine affected premature babies differently from full-term babies.[14] In another AEC study, researchers at the University of Nebraska College of Medicine fed iodine-131 to 28 healthy infants through a gastric tube to test the concentration of iodine in the infants' thyroid glands.

Radioactive iodine experiments refer to a series of studies and experiments conducted in the mid-20th century involving the administration of radioactive iodine to individuals for research purposes. These experiments aimed to study the metabolism and distribution of iodine in the human body, particularly in relation to the thyroid gland. However, many of these experiments were conducted without proper informed consent and ethical oversight, leading to serious health risks for participants.

Some notable examples of radioactive iodine experiments include:

1. **The Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) Experiments (1946-1947):** Researchers at MIT conducted experiments involving the administration of radioactive iodine to patients with thyroid disorders to study iodine metabolism. Informed consent was often lacking, and participants were not fully informed of the risks involved.
2. **The Human Radiation Experiments (1940s-1970s):** Various studies conducted during the era of Cold War nuclear testing involved exposing patients to radiation, including radioactive iodine. One notable example is the injection of radioactive iodine into patients' thyroids to measure the thyroid's function and radiation absorption.
3. **The Hanna Mining Experiments (1950s-1960s):** Hanna Mining Company conducted experiments on workers in an iron ore mine, involving the administration of radioactive iodine to study the effects of dust inhalation on thyroid function. Informed consent was lacking, and workers were not made aware of the radiation exposure.
4. **The Wrentham State School Experiments (1950s-1960s):** Radioactive iodine was administered to residents of Wrentham State School in Massachusetts, which housed individuals with developmental disabilities. The experiments aimed to study iodine absorption in different populations.

These experiments raised significant ethical concerns due to the lack of informed consent, inadequate oversight, and potential health risks to participants. Many participants were exposed to radiation without their knowledge and faced potential long-term health consequences. The revelations of these experiments, along with other unethical medical research practices, led to increased awareness of the importance of research ethics and the protection of human subjects. These events have influenced the development of ethical guidelines and regulations for medical research, ensuring that future studies prioritize the well-being and rights of research participants.

Death of Prescription Drugs

Rebecca Riley, the daughter of Michael and Carolyn Riley of Massachusetts, was found dead in her home at age four, her lungs filled with fluid, after prolonged exposure to various medications. The medical examiner's office determined the girl died from "intoxication due to the combined effects" of prescription drugs. Police reports state she was taking 750 milligrams a day of Depakote, 200 milligrams a day of Seroquel, and .35 milligrams a day of Clonidine. Rebecca had been taking the drugs since the age of two for bipolar disorder and ADHD, diagnosed by child psychiatrist Kayoko Kifuji of the Tufts-New England Medical Center.

Roberto Dreyfus was a French sports physician who became known for his involvement in providing athletes, including cyclists, with performance-enhancing drugs such as erythropoietin (EPO) during the 1990s. EPO is a hormone that increases red blood cell production, which can enhance oxygen delivery to muscles and improve endurance, but its misuse can have serious health risks.

Key Aspects of the Case:

1. **Doping Scandal:** The Roberto Dreyfus Case was part of a larger doping scandal within professional cycling during the 1990s, where athletes were using banned substances to gain a competitive edge.
2. **Health Risks:** The administration of high doses of EPO and other performance-enhancing drugs can pose significant health risks, including blood thickening (which can lead to increased risk of blood clots and stroke), heart problems, and other complications.
3. **Ethical Dilemmas:** This case brought attention to the ethical dilemmas surrounding the use of performance-enhancing drugs in sports. It raised questions about the fairness of competition, the impact on athletes' health, and the role of medical professionals in facilitating or preventing doping.
4. **Responsibility of Physicians:** The case highlighted the ethical responsibilities of physicians in sports medicine. Physicians have a duty to prioritize the well-being of athletes and avoid practices that could harm their health.
5. **Regulation and Oversight:** The case emphasized the need for stronger regulations, testing, and oversight to prevent doping in sports and protect the integrity of athletic competitions.

Cases like the Roberto Dreyfus Case have led to changes in sports regulations, anti-doping efforts, and increased awareness about the ethical considerations surrounding performance-enhancing substances. The World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA) was established to combat doping in sports and ensure fair competition while safeguarding athletes' health.

Assisted suicide				
Case	Country	Location	Year	Summary
<u>Betty and George Coumbias</u>	<u>Canada</u>	<u>Vancouver, British Columbia</u>	2007	A couple request the legal right to commit suicide together, although only the husband was ill.
<u>Dax Cowart</u>	United States		1973	A man who suffered severe burns requests the right to die.
<u>Giovanni Nuvoli</u>	Italy	<u>Alghero, Sardinia</u>	2007	A man in pain requests a legal right to die.
<u>Sue Rodriguez</u>	Canada	<u>Victoria, British Columbia</u>	1991	A woman requests a right to assisted suicide.
<u>Ramón Sampedro</u>	Spain	<u>Galicia</u>	1998	For 29 years a man requests his right to assisted suicide.
<u>Aruna Shanbaug case</u>	India	<u>Karnataka</u>	2011	A writ petition under Article 32 of the Constitution has been filed on behalf of the petitioner Aruna Ramachandra Shanbaug by one Ms. Pinki Virani of Mumbai, claiming to be a next friend.
<u>Piergiorgio Welby</u>	Italy	<u>Rome</u>	2006	A patient requests a legal right to die.

Person wishes for euthanasia for another

Euthanasia of another				
case	country	location	year	summary
<u>Andrew Bedner</u>	United States	<u>White River Junction, Vermont</u>	2008	A parent is charged with critically harming his child who is on life support. If the child dies, the parent may be charged with murder. At question was whether parents should be legally allowed to make medical decisions for children they have allegedly abused.
<u>Tony Bland</u>	England	<u>Sheffield</u>	1993	Bland was the first patient in English legal history to be allowed to die by the courts

				through the withdrawal of life-prolonging treatment.
<u>Carol Carr</u>	United States	<u>Georgia</u>	2002	A mother euthanizes her adult sons to relieve their suffering from <u>Huntington's disease</u> .
<u>Cruzan v. Director, Missouri Department of Health</u>	United States	<u>Missouri</u>	1990	The parents of a woman in a persistent vegetative state request the right to remove her life support equipment.
<u>Eluana Englaro</u>	<u>Italy</u>	<u>Lecco</u>	1992	Parents receive permission to remove the life support from a woman in a persistent vegetative state for 17 years.
<u>June Hartley</u>	United States	<u>California</u>	2009	A sister is charged with euthanizing her brother after he has medical problems.
<u>Jack Kevorkian</u>	United States	Michigan	1994	A medical doctor advocates for <u>assisted suicide</u> and the <u>right to die</u> .
<u>Robert Latimer</u>	Canada	<u>Saskatchewan</u>	1993	A man euthanizes his child who has lived for years in pain.
<u>Karen Ann Quinlan case</u>	United States	New Jersey	1976	A 21-year-old girl is in a persistent vegetative state. Her parents wish to remove her from artificial respiration.
<u>Terri Schiavo case</u>	United States	<u>Florida</u>	2005	A woman is in a persistent vegetative state. Her husband wishes to remove her life support. Her parents wish her to remain on life support.
<u>Marlise Munoz</u>	United States	<u>Texas</u>	2013	A woman was declared brain-dead by her physician. Her husband and family wished to remove life support. The hospital persisted in keeping her on life support because it claims it cannot legally withdraw life support from a pregnant patient.